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 Vision: Journal of Biomedical Research & Environmental Sciences main aim is to enhance the importance of science and technology to the scientific community and also to provide an equal opportunity to seek and share ideas to all our researchers and scientists without any barriers to develop their career and helping in their development of discovering the world.

OPINION

The Limitations of Material Science- Could the Rather Limited, Mechanistic, So-Called “Scientific Approach” to Knowledge be Holding us Back? (Jan 2021)

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The Interactive Communication Systems Involved in the Human Body Go Much Deeper than those that are Normally Described in Most Human Anatomy and Physiology Books

I still have in my possession a Chladni plate. It is one that I constructed myself as a young lad interested in studying science. It was a way to investigate the vibrational effect that different sound frequencies had on the physical distribution and patterns formed by sand on a metal plate that is vibrated at different frequencies. The areas of greater vibrational amplitude would drive the sand away from the surface to other places of lower vibrational amplitude. It was fascinating to watch different beautiful patterns that would immerge when the plate was subjected to different sound frequencies.

Many years later, I set up a demonstration at the Mind/Body/Spirit exhibition at Olympia. It involved electronically wiring up a young living shrub to an oscilloscope. Any change in the electronic resonance of the plant would result demonstrably in changing the pattern displayed on the oscilloscope. Visitors were encouraged to focus on the shrub in question and mentally direct their thoughts to it. Concurrently they were able to observe changes that occurred on the patterns displayed on the oscilloscope. These could be visibly seen to change, depending on the nature of thoughts and feelings that were directed to the plant in question.

As far as I was concerned, this was a practical illustration, and an example of the fact that mental energy given off by human beings and directed towards another living entity, in this case, a living shrub, had a measurable physical and physiological effect on the plant to which it was directed

This was a simple practical demonstration of the fact that the thoughts and feelings of people have also sent out vibrational effects in the surrounding atmosphere that can provoke demonstrable effects on other living things; even other living plants which do not possess neurological structures anything like those that exist within other living entities such as animals that have physical senses and a nervous system and anatomical structures that are very much more comparable to those of mankind. This is not something that anyone who has a loving caring relationship with plants would be in any way surprised to know.

Science is based on a rational, logical approach to thinking. In anatomical terms, some neuroscience researchers believe that the function of the human brain is best explained by the concept of lateralization, meaning that the right and left

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hemispheres of the brain perform different functions and that the two communicate through their connections. This way of thinking is appreciated amongst many of the people who are regarded as being more educated and aware of facts and figures in a scientific way.

It is something that those of us who have been privileged to have benefited from an orthodox educational system should be most grateful for. It relates to the enormous benefits that science has been able to provide for many of us in recent times.

In contrast to this, and in more conventional simple terms, the artistic, more creative, imaginative aspects of the mind are more readily associated with the Right side of the brain. A balanced approach to these distinctions may involve valuing both aspects and integrating them together in a more balanced way.

It should not be forgotten, that for many thousands of years, there have been groups and communities of human beings in different parts of the world who have found healthy fulfilling ways to live to old age and get on with each other very successfully. They did not have in their possession all the wonderful gadgets and materials that many people, in some regions, may take for granted and feel that they are more developed. So, what could the factors be that would enable us to reconcile the differences outlined possibly be?

I would suggest that they relate to vibrational frequencies. Although they may not be so obvious to the normal physical senses, they are given out, received, and responded to, often not in such a conscious way, by most people and even other living entities. They include such feelings as Friendship, Empathy, and Intuition. To many, they are also associated with love and respect. When Humanism of this kind is extended to valuing and holding in owe the amazing mysterious miracle of creation and life itself which as far as we know, is unique to this planet, we should certainly count

our blessings. And as David Attenborough expressed so succinctly in his book: 'A Life on Our Planet', (ISBN 948-1-529-10827-9), "all life is interconnected in a web of infinite variety, with everything relying on everything else."

Historically, different cultures have described, classified, and named some of the life-giving energy fields in different ways. Terms such as Auras, Chakras, and Meridians and lifer energy fields have been used. They can be shown to be associated with different nerve plexuses, such as those associated with the eyes, ears, throat, heart, digestive system, and reproductive system. In a balanced healthy person, together with the mind, they all work together in harmony in relation to the activities and wide environment in which a person is operating.

In addition to this, it can be demonstrated, in measurable ways, that there are numbers of different overlapping energy fields that progressively radiate out different distances from the physical body. These include what are termed the Etheric, Astral, Mental, and Spiritual/Causal body.

A wide variety of interest groups exist. The literature that they publish tends to focus on different aspects of what it is to be human. For example, 'Paradigm Explorer' (Ref. explore.scimednet.org), is published by the Scientific and Medical Network, a leading international forum for people engaged in creating a new worldview for the 21st century. It has published many open-minded articles about the nature of the relationship that exists between the physical, biological, mental, emotional, religious, and spiritual aspects of humanity. And the relationships that these can have on the ongoing health and vitality of all human beings.

The Diagram Below is to Illustrates the Interconnected Relationships that Need to Exist in a Balanced Way Between Different Aspects of the Energetic Life-Enhancing Ecosystem of the Earth

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